

Spectroscopic, Antifungal and Antibacterial Studies of some Manganese Heterochelates

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Manuscript received 19 November 1993, revised 21 October 1994, accepted 4 November 1994

In our earlier publications several new Mn^{II} homoche-
lates of different types of azomethines have been
reported^{1,2}. However, there seems to be no report
on heterochelates of such ligands. Here we describe
the spectroscopic, antifungal and antibacterial studies
of some of the biologically active manganese(II)
heterochelates of monofunctional bidentate ligands
having NS and NO donor sets.

Results and Discussion

The reactions between hydrated manganese
dichloride and monobasic bidentate thiosemicar-
bazones and semicarbazones in 1 : 1 : 1 molar
ratio in methanol resulted in the replacement of
chlorides and isolation of $[Mn(SCZ)(SCZ')]$ and
 $[Mn(SCZ)(TSCZ')]$ types of complexes (yields 75–
85%). The reactions are quite facile and the resulting
coloured solids are soluble in methanol, DMF and
DMSO. Molecular weight data showed them to be
monomers. They are non-electrolytes having molar
conductance values ($10^3 M$ solution) in the range
 $10-15 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$. The magnetic moment values
of the complexes are in the range 5.90–6.02 B.M.,
suggesting a high-spin state for these complexes².

The esr spectra of $[Mn(SCZ)(SCZ)_2]$ at room
temperature showed only one isotropic signal
centered at $g = 2.016$. The spectrum of the complex
is expected of high-spin $S = 5/2$ species, and is
similar to the spectra of other such molecules³. Earlier
workers reported esr spectra for closely related Mn^{II}
complexes and assigned a tetrahedral geometry². At-
tempt to determine isotropic hyperfine coupling con-
stants of sample at room temperature was unsuc-
cessful, since the spectrum consisted only of a very
broad featureless resonance at $g = 2.016$.

The electronic spectra of the complexes in the
visible region showed weak absorptions at 21 929
and 23 809 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^6A_1-{}^4E$
(G) and ${}^6A_1-{}^4E_1$ (G) transitions respectively, sug-
gesting a tetrahedral environment around the metal
ion. Strong bands around 37 735–37 313, 34 482–
31 746 and 31 250–29 761 cm^{-1} have been tentatively
assigned to charge transfer band of the ligands⁴.

The thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones
studied, exist in tautomeric forms, as evidenced from
the infrared spectral data. A broad and strong band
at 3 300–3 100 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the hydrogen
bonded NH/OH overlapping with CH stretching
vibrations of aromatic rings. The ν_{NH} band along
with $\nu_{C=S}$ and $\nu_{C=O}$ bands disappeared in the solution
spectra of ligands and a new band at ca. 2 570
 cm^{-1} (SH) was observed indicating tautomerisation
of the ligands.

On complexation, these bands disappeared comple-
tely, thereby confirming coordination of the ligand
to the manganese atom. The free ligands displayed
two sharp bands at ca. 3 440 and 3 320 cm^{-1}
due to the asymmetric and symmetric modes of

NH₂ group respectively, which remained unchanged in the metal chelates indicating their non-participation in chelation. The $\nu_{C=S}$ band is strongly coupled in nearly all the compounds in which the carbon is directly linked to nitrogen. In the spectra of all the ligands, strong bands appearing at 840–800 and 1 100–1 040 cm⁻¹ attributable respectively to nearly pure $\nu_{C=S}$ and $\nu_{C=S}$ coupled with N–C–N– stretching of N–N stretching and N–C–N– deformation vibration, were observed⁵. In the spectra of the corresponding metal heterochelates, these bands disappeared. Appearance of a new sharp band, simultaneously at 700–600 cm⁻¹ (C–S)⁵ could be taken as evidence of the ligands coordinating via thioenol structure. A strong band at ~1 690 cm⁻¹ in all the semicarbazones is the characteristic band of the carbonyl group. The absence of this band in the complexes indicates the disappearance of $\nu_{C=O}$ band due to enolisation and a new band at ~1 640 cm⁻¹ is observed on account of the formation of C=N–N=C group⁶.

The use of absorption due to C=N stretching frequency in identifying the bonding site is somewhat limited because of the complex nature of absorption in the region 1 550–1 630 cm⁻¹. However, a strong peak of the ligands at ~1 610 cm⁻¹ registered substantial decrease in the intensity after complex formation. This band may be assigned to complex vibration involving $\nu_{C=N}$, δ_{NH_2} and the aromatic

ring⁷. The bonding of the metal ions with C=N moiety contributes to the decrease of the intensity of their ligand band (Table 1). The ν_{N-N} band of the ligands at ~1 050 cm⁻¹ shifted by ~10 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. The negative shift in $\nu_{C=N}$ and positive shift in ν_{N-N} are characteristic of coordination through azomethine nitrogen.

The ir spectral studies indicate that the thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones behave as a mononegative bidentate ligands coordination sites being deprotonated enolic oxygen/thiolic sulphur and azomethine nitrogen.

Fungicidal and bactericidal activities :

All the free ligands and their corresponding heterochelates were tested on some pathogenic fungi and bacteria. The results show that the metal heterochelates are more active than the parent ligands. The enhanced activities of the metal chelates compared to the free ligands can be ascribed to increased lipophilic nature of these complexes arising due to chelation¹. Solubility of the compounds also plays an important role in ascertaining the degree of inhibition. Metal complexes of the ligands having sulphur as a donor atom were found to be more potent than those without sulphur. It has been proposed that the ultimate action of structurally non-specific toxicants is the denaturation of one or more proteins of the cell. Chelating agents are often powerful

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF THE Mn^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, M.p. °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-S}
	Mn	N	S					
[Mn(SCZ) (SCZ ₁)] (Light brown, 220d)	12.53 (12.68)	19.14 (19.39)	—	418 (433)	1 580	450	390	—
[Mn(SCZ) (SCZ ₂)] (Cream, 165d)	21.42 (21.59)	14.08 (14.12)	—	352 (389)	1 595	480	410	—
[Mn(SCZ) (SCZ ₃)] (Brown, 140)	14.69 (14.69)	22.33 (22.52)	—	348 (373)	1 590	470	420	—
[Mn(SCZ) (SCZ ₄)] (Yellow, 170)	14.22 (14.30)	25.43 (25.52)	—	358 (384)	1 585	460	370	—
[Mn(SCZ) (TSCZ ₁)] (Brown, 120)	15.69 (15.74)	23.91 (24.06)	9.12 (9.18)	326 (349)	1 590	—	405	320
[Mn(SCZ) (TSCZ ₂)] (Cream, 100)	13.49 (13.56)	20.67 (20.74)	15.78 (15.83)	385 (405)	1 595	—	410	290
[Mn(SCZ) (TSCZ ₃)] (Yellow, 112)	14.08 (14.12)	21.50 (21.59)	8.11 (8.24)	364 (389)	1 595	—	395	315
[Mn(SCZ) (TSCZ ₄)] (Yellow, 160d)	13.65 (13.73)	24.41 (24.50)	7.92 (8.01)	372 (400)	1 590	—	385	340

inhibitors of metalloenzymes, so it may be postulated that the ligands may act by inhibiting the enzymes whose activity depends on metals.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared by the reported methods⁸ and analysed. For the sake of convenience these have been abbreviated as 2-furfuraldehyde semicarbazone (HSCZ), 2-acetylnaphthalene semicarbazone (HSCZ₁), 2-acetylthiophene semicarbazone (HSCZ₂), 2-acetylfuran semicarbazone (HSCZ₃), 2-acetylpyridine semicarbazone (HSCZ₄), 2-acetylnaphthalene thiosemicarbazone (HTSCZ₁), 2-acetylthiophene thiosemicarbazone (HTSCZ₂), 2-acetylfuran thiosemicarbazone (HTSCZ₃) and 2-acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (HTSCZ₄).

All reagents were dried and distilled prior to use.

Preparation of complexes : To a solution of MnCl₂·4H₂O in methanol was added the ligands in equimolar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 8–9 h, then the solvent was removed by distillation and the residue was dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were washed (three times) with dry cyclohexane and dried under reduced pressure for 3–4 h.

Conductivity was measured in dry DMF on a Systronics 305 conductivity bridge and molecular weight by Rast camphor method. Magnetic measurement was carried out at room temperature by a vibrating sample magnetometer (model 155). Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (methanol) on a Pye-Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a X-band Varian spectrophotometer in the solid state at room temperature.

Manganese, chlorine, nitrogen and sulphur were estimated as reported elsewhere¹.

Biological activities : The antifungal activity was evaluated against *Macrophomina phaseolina* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by the agar-plate technique concentrations at 200, 100 and 50 ppm using a fine suspension of the complex in methanol. The number of replications in each case was three. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of colony after 96 h and the percentage inhibition was calculated.

The bactericidal activity was evaluated by the paper-disc plate method⁹. The nutrient agar medium (peptone, beef extract, NaCl and agar-agar) and 5 mm diameter paper-disc of Whatman no. 1 were used. The compounds were dissolved in methanol in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations and tested against *Xanthomonas sp.*, *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and the inhibition zone was measured.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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